

Dynamic Service Provisioning and Control Relying on Time-Varying Telemetry-Driven QoT Digital-Twin

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Abstract—This paper presents an orchestration and control architecture for multi-domain optical networks. The proposed solution improves performance predictability by leveraging a modular, closed-loop SDN control plane that enables dynamic service provisioning, optimal path selection, and amplifier control. A key innovation is the integration of a time-varying QoT Digital Twin, which exploits live telemetry to enhance real-time decision-making and network adaptability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of data traffic and the increasing demand for high-speed, reliable connectivity have driven the need for continuous advancements in optical network technology. As networks grow in complexity, manual management becomes insufficient, requiring a shift toward software-based control to ensure efficient, scalable, and adaptive operations [1]. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a crucial enabler in this shift, providing a centralized, flexible approach to manage and dynamically configure network devices across multi-vendor environments [2]. Paired with a network orchestrator, the SDN controller supports coordination across network layers, enhancing the ability to automate service provisioning and optimize resources. Standardized interfaces and data models are essential to this SDN-driven architecture, promoting compatibility among diverse network components and simplifying integration. Standardized approaches like OpenROADM [3] support interoperability, future-proofing network design and enabling flexible scaling as technology advances. In addition to the SDN-enabled control foundation, the Digital Twin (DT) concept has emerged as a powerful tool for real-time network monitoring, simulation, and optimization. A DT acts as a virtual replica of the

physical network, allowing operators to predict and mitigate potential issues, optimize network performance, and implement proactive maintenance strategies, ultimately reducing downtime and operational costs. By integrating SDN control with the DT, operators can achieve a live, telemetry-driven model that dynamically reflects the current network state, providing timely insights for Quality of Transmission (QoT) estimation and adaptive management.

This paper demonstrates dynamic service provisioning, extending previous work in QoT estimation [4]. We incorporate innovations in DT technology, including closed-loop amplifier control, real-time telemetry, and the use of an OpenROADM-compatible SDN interface. This standards-based, SDN-enabled DT architecture enables adaptive QoT management, enhances network reliability, and highlights the role of open standards in achieving interoperable, vendor-agnostic solutions for high-demand optical networks. One of the key innovations presented in this paper is the integration of a live telemetry plane (TP), enabling direct and continuous data collection from network devices to keep the DT in sync with the real network. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on static or delayed data inputs, this real-time telemetry framework ensures that the DT accurately reflects the network's current operational state, allowing for refreshed QoT estimation and proactive adjustments. The TP is designed to both collect and distribute data across different control layers and network orchestrator acting as both producers and consumers of telemetry. This bidirectional flow of information improves network visibility, supports closed-loop control mechanisms, and enables rapid adaptation to changing conditions, ultimately improving the efficiency and reliability of optical network operations. By demonstrating the interplay between SDN, standardized models, and DT, this work underscores significant advancements in real-time QoT estimation and reliable, automated network operation.

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including specific vendor technologies, device configurations, and network policies. The SDN controller for each domain provides a standardized control layer, allowing it to manage resources such as spectrum allocation, wavelength assignment. Through the use of inter-domain protocols and interfaces, the controllers exchange essential information such as topology, resource availability, and service capabilities. This information exchange allows the coordinated setup of services spanning multiple domains without revealing sensitive details of each domain’s internal structure. The SDN controller continuously monitors the performance of its domain, gathering telemetry data such as optical signal-to-noise ratios (SNR), channel power levels, and spectral utilization. Based on these inputs, it can dynamically adjust network configurations to optimize performance or respond to failures. In addition to supporting automation and optimization, SDN controllers are crucial for achieving vendor-agnostic management in disaggregated optical networks. By leveraging open standards and APIs, such as NETCONF, or RESTful interfaces, the controller abstracts vendor-specific details and provides a unified view of the domain to the orchestrator. This capability not only simplifies network operations but also enhances interoperability between devices from different manufacturers. In this context, devices characteristics and capabilities can be exposed using standard models. In this scenario, OpenROADM and OpenConfig models are the most used and validated [6].

C. Optical Multiplex Section Controller

One of the key innovations introduced in this paper is the inclusion of an Optical Multiplex Section (OMS) controller [12] in the overall control architecture. The introduction of the OMS controller adds a layer of detailed, localized control specifically dedicated to the operation of amplifiers, such as Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers (EDFAs) and Raman

amplifiers. This novel approach enables real-time, dynamic adjustments of parameters like amplifier gain, tilt, and power levels. A key feature of the OMS controller is its deep awareness of the physical details of the network. This includes detailed knowledge of network components, such as fiber types, amplifier configurations, and the specific characteristics of optical transmission. Additionally, by tracking real-time metrics like input and output power levels, the controller can autonomously detect faults or performance degradations and take immediate corrective actions, either locally or in coordination with the network orchestrator [7].

D. Devices Agent

The main feature of disaggregated networks is the exploitation of devices provided by different vendors, but their integration within control plane requires a common model and open interfaces. In reality, most devices are running distinct operating systems that implement only their own proprietary languages. As a result, the interoperability between the SDN controller and the devices it manages is critical. Some devices already support the necessary standard models in their own operating systems and, as a consequence, no further actions are required. On the contrary, the devices that are not featured by standard models require an additional component to guarantee the interoperability. For this purpose, software agents have been developed. An agent is a middleware component that collects commands from the controller, written according to a standard, and translates them into the proprietary model supported by the devices [8]. In this scenario, the SDN controller communicates only with the agent, which consequently forwards the processed requests towards the respective devices.

E. Digital Twin

The importance of DT in optical networks is well established [9]. In this scenario, the DT is integrated not only within the SDN context but also leverages telemetry data to ensure it remains automatically and continuously updated. By creating an up-to-date virtual version of the network, it allows network operators to monitor the state of the physical network in real time, offering insights that enable proactive management and optimization. The DT in an optical network combines telemetry data - also known as Digital Shadow (DS) - with the optical network digital model, to create an up to date DT of the entire network. With a continuous stream of data from devices like the OMS controller, the DT mirrors the physical state of the network, creating an accurate virtual model that reflects the system’s dynamic behavior. One of the main advantages of having a DT in optical networks is the ability to simulate the network’s response to different scenarios. Since the DT incorporates real-time telemetry from devices such as amplifiers, the virtual model can predict the effects of various configurations, faults, or disturbances, providing network operators with invaluable foresight. For example, by simulating the impact of introducing new channels or adjusting amplifier parameters, the DT can inform network decisions

Fig. 2: Grafana acquisition shown the EDFAs Gain and Input power evolution across the time.

Fig. 3: Network orchestrator GUI displaying topology data collected from various controllers. FO collect both ROADM and OMS info: in red circle ROADMs, blue squares OMSs. Other devices are the TRX and the interconnections link

Fig. 4: Link status displayed in the upper section, with the ONOS SDN GUI shown below.

before any physical changes are made, effectively reducing the risk of performance degradation or failure.

F. Telemetry Plane

In optical networks, the TP serves as a critical channel for collecting and transferring real-time data across various network components. Controllers such as the orchestrator, SDN controller, and OMS controller play key roles as both producers and consumers of telemetry information. As producers, these controllers collect performance data from network elements like amplifiers and multiplexers. For instance, an OMS controller tracks amplifier parameters such as gain, tilt and optical power (Fig.2), generating telemetry that provides insight into network health. Similarly, the SDN controller collects data on traffic, topology, and link status. On the other hand, these controllers also act as consumers of telemetry data, using the information gathered by other parts of the network to optimize decision-making. The main novelty introduced by this paper is the exploitation of the TP to create a time-varying DT. The importance of the updated DT is crucial for application like self-healing of the optical network and live QoT-e [7].

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP & WORKFLOW

This paper setup - hosted at the LINKS Foundation laboratories located in Turin, Italy (Fig. 5) - reproduces a multivendor optical core network with 3 Adtran ROADMs and as many bidirectional optical lines (520, 220, 210 km long, respectively). Two lines are amplified by Juniper amplifiers and one by Cisco amplifiers. As part of the paper innovations, a dedicated OMS Controller is responsible for the configuration

and telemetry of the line components. Traffic is injected via 6 pluggable transponders (TRX): 4 in the Cassini Whiteboxes, and 2 in the Galileo Phoenix.

According with the previous section, the control plane architecture has been implemented as follow:

- i. FlexOpt (FO) [10] as network orchestrator (Fig. 3). Its role includes receiving traffic requests - Dynamic Service Request (DSR), according to the TAPI standard [11] - and collecting topology details from the software components

Fig. 5: Physical setup of the network demonstration.

Fig. 6: Sequence chart illustrating the complete workflow of the paper.

- described below. This enables it to apply a routing algorithm based on the GSNR value.
- ii. ONOS [13] as SDN controller (Fig. 4): in our topology, the SDN controller manages the ROADMs and transponders. For this experiment, ONOS has been extended to support the latest version of the OpenROADM standard.
 - iii. OMS Controller: One of the key innovations introduced in this paper is the inclusion of an OMS controller [12], which allows for the retrieval of amplifier working points directly from the network. This brings several advantages: first, the DT instance can be automatically updated without manual input, as data are saved by the OMS in the telemetry plane, which the DT then uses for its updates; second, with individual OMS instances, it becomes possible to obtain GSNR values per OMS.
 - iv. Since each Adtran operates with an operating system that only supports a proprietary model, which is incompatible with the OpenROADM standard, an agent called OpenROADM agent has been created and placed between ONOS and each ROADM device. In this scenario, where 3 ROADMs are used, 3 equal OpenROADM agents [8] are required. The role of this software is to collect commands from ONOS, which are written according to the OpenROADM standard. Then, those commands are processed and converted into specific requests that are compatible with the proprietary language of the device that must execute the task. Since ONOS must be aware of the composition of each device, the agent is also developed to expose the hardware characteristics of the device it is linked to. In this way, ONOS is aware of the structure of the ROADMs and can deliver the right commands to set up new connections, or to delete the already existing ones (see Fig.8).
 - v. GNPY as Network DT: The importance of DT in optical networks is well established [9]. In this scenario, the DT is integrated not only within the SDN context but also

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[10:08:01.869109] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: tn gsnr 100 ~
[10:08:01.869158] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: retrieve http://montebianco.polito.it:9849/api-v0/
manager_client.hpp:124
[10:08:02.068326] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: tn gsnr 25 ~
[10:08:02.068448] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: retrieve http://montebianco.polito.it:9849/api-v0/
manager_client.hpp:124
[10:08:02.211180] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: tn gsnr 25 ~
[10:08:02.211303] 4317 [D] [link_manager]: retrieve http://montebianco.polito.it:9849/api-v0/

[10:09:33.363355] 4307 [D] [ONOS_WRAPPER] sending opmode config
{"uuid": "9f7fe82d-94d9-43e7-ad70-f98390359aed", "appId": "org.onosproject.optical-rest", "ingressP
92.168.88.12:830", "port": "10", "opModeId": "2108"}, /home/rcasellas/src/spce/src/server/plugins
[10:09:33.363379] 4307 [D] [ONOS_WRAPPER][send_intent] POSTing intent ~ /h
[10:09:33.512951] 4307 [I] [ONOS_WRAPPER]: send_intent result [http://montebianco.polito.it/onos
gins/onos/controller.cpp:1239
[10:09:33.928780] 4307 [I] [ONOS_WRAPPER]: opModeConfigure response 200 ~ /h
[10:09:33.928900] 4307 [I] [ONOS_WRAPPER]: opModeConfigure ec Success ~ /h

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Fig. 7: Screenshots of data exchange—upper section displays GSNR data from the OMS controller, while the lower section shows the opcode settings for the transceiver obtained from the DT.

- leverages telemetry data to ensure it remains automatically and continuously updated.
- vi. This paper follows the telemetry platform defined in [14]. In particular, InfluxDB is used as main database. It has been widely used for telemetry purposes as it is a time series database. Data is periodically sent to the database via different controllers. In particular, the authors have developed python scripts that are called by telegraf that injects the data into the database. These scripts exploit the REST interfaces of the different controllers to obtain the data. This allows to have a completely vendor-independent telemetry. Finally, the observability of the system is guaranteed using Grafana.

The validation of the described architecture is conducted using the setup described in the previous sections and is structured into two main phases (Fig. 6).

The first phase consists of network probing, during which the FO orchestrator collects data from both the ONOS SDN controllers of individual domains and the various OMS controllers. The SDN controller not only shares the network topology but also provides the available modulation formats (MF) in the form of OpCodes. Additionally, the different OMS controllers, being aware of the physical details of the network, can leverage GNPY to estimate the GSNR for each optical path. This GSNR estimation is then used in the path computation process. By the end of this phase, the FO has a complete and detailed view of the network topology.

The second phase is triggered by a TAPI DSR [11] request to the FO. At this point, the FO utilizes the previously obtained GSNR estimations to perform a GSNR-based routing algorithm. Once the optimal path is selected, the FO forwards both the path and its physical characteristics to the DT for validation. Furthermore, the authors have extended the DT model by incorporating back-to-back characterizations of transceivers [15]. This enhancement allows the DT not only to validate the selected path, but also to return the optimal MF.

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netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG1-WSS (circuit-pack)
->Generating token...

DEG1-WSS-IN10 -> DEG1-WSS-TX (fc = 194500000, w = 50000)

netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG2-AMPRX (dummy-amp)
netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG2-AMPTX (dummy-amp)
netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG2-WSS (circuit-pack)

DEG2-WSS-IN10 -> DEG2-WSS-TX (fc = 195500000, w = 50000)

netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG3-AMPRX (dummy-amp)
netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG3-AMPTX (dummy-amp)
netopeer-server[1]: Transapi calling callback /A:org-openroadm-device
netopeer-server[1]: Initializing circuit-pack DEG3-WSS (circuit-pack)

DEG3-WSS-IN10 -> DEG3-WSS-TX (fc = 195500000, w = 50000)

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Fig. 8: Screenshot of the OpenROADM agent. The agent is retrieving information about the pre-existing connections for each degree of the ROADM.

Finally, the FO delegates the configuration of the ROADMs and transceivers to the SDN controller, using the validated path and mapping the chosen MF to the OpCodes received during the probing phase. ONOS configures the devices using either OpenConfig or OpenROADM data models.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 3 illustrates how the FO successfully retrieves topology data from ONOS, whose network representation is depicted in Fig. 4. It is important to note that ONOS lacks any detailed information regarding the composition of the OMS, whereas the FO is able to obtain these details through the data exchange mechanism shown in Fig 7.

Specifically, Fig 7 presents the GSNR values obtained for several optical paths and the corresponding MF validation. Since, for the ONOS controller and FO orchestrator, the links between ROADMs and transceivers are handled as links equivalent to OMS, the authors have set the GSNR values for these specific links to 100. However, despite this simplification, these impedance effects are still accurately modeled within the DT. The primary motivation behind this approach is to prevent these specific link characteristics from influencing the GSNR-based routing algorithm while maintaining a realistic network representation within the DT.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents several innovative advancements in optical network management. One key aspect is the integration of an OMS controller, which allows direct access to real-time amplifier data, such as gain and tilt settings. In addition, the paper enables continuous synchronization of the DT through telemetry integration. By linking the OMS and telemetry plane, the DT remains dynamically aligned with the network's real-time state, enhancing the accuracy of QoT insights. The SDN controller used in this paper

has also been enhanced to support the latest OpenROADM standard. To achieve this in a multi-vendor environment, an OpenROADM agent was developed, bridging compatibility gaps by translating standardized OpenROADM commands into proprietary formats specific to the lab devices. Finally, the paper introduces a GSNR-driven routing approach, which elevates routing decisions to a QoT-focused level. By using GSNR as a central metric, the paper enables precise path selection, ensuring high throughput and network resilience aligned with QoT requirements. This GSNR-based routing paradigm shifts network operations toward more responsive, quality-oriented management, a necessity for next-generation, high-performance applications.

For future evolution, we aim to enhance both soft and hard failure recovery capabilities. This will include mechanisms for traffic restoration and dynamic configuration adjustments, ensuring the network can swiftly reinstate services or optimize settings in response to faults. By focusing on adaptive recovery, we intend to create a more resilient and self-healing optical network capable of minimizing downtime and maintaining service continuity.

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